

An investigation into the development and performance of hybrid materials within 3D printing

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Declaration

We declare that this report and the studies described herein are our own.

Where we have consulted the work of others (including published research and/or internet sources), these are clearly stated and appropriately referenced within the Bibliography.

We have personally designed and conducted the tests and performed the data analysis presented in this paper. We have been supported by our mentors – Mr Alex Rothman (Teacher of Physics) and Mr Hamish Chandler (Teacher of Design & Engineering). Their role was to provide occasional high-level conceptual guidance, safety oversight, and access to specialised lab equipment.

We confirm that the core practical work and the writing of this report were completed by us, without any use of generative AI.

We have both contributed equally to this study and report in terms of time, content and effort and have spent over 70 hours each on this project.

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Abstract

3D printing is a form of additive manufacturing, where physical objects are fabricated by joining materials (in the form of long strips of polymers called filament), thereby reducing waste. As 3D printing continues to develop, new materials need to be created based on their advantageous properties, such as tensile strength, thermal endurance, and impact strength.

In this project, the authors investigated how it could be possible to combine two common materials used in 3D printing – Polylactic Acid (PLA) and Thermoplastic Polyurethane (TPU). PLA is biodegradable and easy to print but is brittle, making it unsuitable for small parts. On the other hand, TPU is flexible and has good layer adhesion, but is difficult to print. By combining the two materials to create a hybrid material, the authors hypothesised that the hybrid material's properties would be in between those of PLA and TPU.

This report outlines the method in which a hybrid material can easily be recreated on a 3D printer in a non-industrial/domestic environment.

The report also investigates the performance of the hybrid material, compared to the PLA and TPU. The performance of the PLA-TPU hybrid was assessed by adapting standardised tensile, heat, compression and impact tests.

The authors concluded that the hybrid material is optimised for more situations than the pure materials, but there are still circumstances where the pure materials are optimal.

Recommendations are made for future studies.

Keywords

Keyword	Definition
Annealing	Annealing is a heat treatment of metals or plastics that restores some of the material's original physical properties. In particular, it increases ductility and decreases hardness
Brittleness	Brittleness is a material property that describes its tendency to fracture with little to no plastic deformation when stress is applied to it
Ductility	Ductility measures a material's capability to undergo permanent plastic deformation when placed under tensile stress
FDM 3D printing	Fused Deposition Modelling (FDM) is a process of additive manufacture which creates three-dimensional objects from digital files by depositing layers of molten thermoplastics
Filament	The long strip (typically stored in a spool) of a thermoplastic polymer that a 3D printer takes in and melts
Glass Transition Temperature	Glass transition temperature is the temperature at which the polymers change its physical state from rigid, brittle state to a soft, flexible, rubbery state
Impact Toughness	Impact toughness is a material's capacity to absorb energy and deform plastically without fracturing under sudden, high-velocity loading or shock
K-factor	A 3D printer setting that adjusts filament extrusion rates during rapid acceleration and deceleration, to equalise pressure within the hotend
Melt Zone	The temperature-controlled zone of the hotend where the filament is heated to its melting temperature by a heater cartridge
PLA	Polylactic Acid (PLA) is a thermoplastic made from renewable organic sources commonly used in 3D printing
Tensile Strength	The amount of tension a material can withstand before failing or breaking
TPU	Thermoplastic Polyurethane (TPU) is a thermoplastic elastomer used in 3D printing
Vicat Softening Temperature	The Vicat Softening temperature is defined as the softening point for materials that have no definite melting point, such as polymers
Young's Modulus (Modulus of Elasticity)	The fundamental material property measuring the stiffness or resistance of a material. Young's Modulus is defined as the ratio of tensile stress and tensile strain

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Introduction

History of 3D Printing

3D printing is a form of additive manufacturing, where physical objects are fabricated by joining materials layer-by-layer, directly from computer-aided design (CAD) models. In contrast to subtractive manufacturing, such as milling or lathing, or formative manufacturing, such as injection moulding, 3D printing only deposits material where it is needed, significantly reducing waste.

3D printing started as an academic experiment. In 1981, Dr. Hideo Kodama invented one of the first machines that used light to harden liquid plastic into shapes (*Kodama, 1981*). The concept was industrialised in 1986 by Chuck Hull, who created the first official 3D printer which used stereolithography – the first commercial 3d printing technology. Soon after, Scott Crump invented Fused Deposition Modelling (FDM) in which thermoplastics can be extruded through a heated nozzle (*Crump, 1992*). This is the most frequently used method in 3D printing and is found in most desktop printers. This is also the method used by the printers used in this project.

Initially, 3D printers were expensive and mostly used by large corporations to make industrial prototypes. Then, in 2005, the RepRap (short for Replicating Rapid Prototyper) Project under Dr. Adrian Bowyer produced a mission to build a low-cost 3D printer that could print its own parts (*Bowyer, 2005*). This made FDM 3D printing much more accessible and affordable for schools and homes.

3D printing is widespread today and growing rapidly (*Protolabs, 2024*). The 3D printing market (including revenue from 3D printing systems, software, materials, and services) has grown from US\$9.4 billion in 2019 to US\$30.2 billion in 2025 and is predicted to be US\$88.3 billion by 2030 (*Figure 1*).

Figure 1: 3D printing market size – actual and forecast (*Protolabs, 2024*)

Use of 3D Printing

With advancement in technology, the use of 3D printing is transitioning from industrial prototyping toward the production of end-use functional parts for different sectors of the economy.

3D printing is now widely used as a part of real-world industries. In medicine, doctors can print custom-fit prosthetic limbs or even titanium bone replacements that match a patient's body perfectly. In aerospace, companies like SpaceX and Boeing use 3D printing to make engine parts that are lighter and stronger than those traditionally. The International Space Station can also 3D print tools in space. 3D Printing is also very popular for hobbies, for example for making detailed gaming miniatures or replacement parts for broken appliances at home.

3D printing is a much more sustainable way to make things, as it only uses the material it needs. It produces significantly less waste compared to traditional subtractive manufacturing methods (Turku et al., 2021).

Need for new 3D Printing materials

As 3D printing becomes more popular and moves beyond prototypes to be used in real life applications, there is need to develop newer, enhanced materials that are useful and sustainable for practical use.

Thermoplastics such as PLA, TPU, ABS, PETG, PC and PA are commonly used in 3D printing. Each of these materials have both advantages and disadvantages. For example, standard PLA is a bio-based thermoplastic and is the most popular 3D printing plastic. It is easy to use and sustainable because it is made from plants. However, PLA has low impact strength making it very brittle, so it snaps easily when dropped or hit. On the other hand, TPU is very flexible and hard to break, but it is unable to hold a heavy load.

In this investigation we wanted to design and create a hybrid material combining two materials to combine the advantageous properties of both. The properties are discussed on the next page.

Investigating hybrid materials for 3D Printing

Having realised that no single thermoplastic fully meets the demands of all applications, we researched six candidate materials for this investigation – PLA, TPU, ABS, PETG, PC and PA.

We eventually decided upon using PLA and TPU for this study because of their relative ease of use and their contrasting properties of rigidity and flexibility, which would provide a clear basis for evaluating whether a hybrid material offers distinct advantages.

The materials which we considered but rejected are listed in Table 1, along with the reasons why we rejected them.

Material:	Rejection reason:
ABS (Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene)	ABS produces toxic fumes when printing and is unsafe to print without a developed ventilation system. It also warps and deforms when printed in an unheated enclosure.
PETG (Polyethylene Terephthalate Glycol)	PETG has aggressive bed adhesion and is prone to stringing, making it difficult to print
PC (Polycarbonate)	PC has low inter-layer adhesion and exceeded our budget for the project and was rejected in the budgeting phase.
PA (Nylon/ Polyamide)	PA has a printing temperature of 280°C, which would cause thermal degradation in most other filaments like PLA, creating a fire hazard. Like ABS, it also requires a heated chamber

Table 1: Alternative materials considered for the Hybrid Filament and reasons for rejection

Tables 2 and 3 compare the key advantages and disadvantages of PLA and TPU material. The main difference between the two is rigidity against flexibility. PLA provides structural strength but snaps under impact, while TPU resists breakage but cannot bear heavy loads. These properties make them strong candidates for combination.

Taken together, PLA's rigidity and biodegradability and TPU's flexibility and thermal resistance suggest that a hybrid of the two could address the weaknesses of each.

Advantageous properties of PLA:	Disadvantageous properties of PLA:
PLA is biodegradable	PLA has a Vicat Softening Temperature of 50°C, making it unsuitable for high temperature environments
PLA is easy to print, as it does not require special conditions such as a heated chamber	PLA is brittle – it lacks flexibility and is prone to snapping in high pressure situations
PLA is safe to print as no fumes are emitted during printing	While water resistant, PLA is not fully waterproof, needing sealants such as epoxy resin for a fully waterproof finish
PLA is a cheap 3D printing filament available for domestic/hobby use at £18/kilogram {Bambu Lab Store, April 2026}).	PLA is not as ductile as TPU, making it unsuitable for applications which need a part to extend

Table 2: Advantages and Disadvantages of PLA

Advantageous properties of TPU:	Disadvantageous properties of TPU:
TPU is flexible and durable, making it a good choice for high-wear parts	TPU is hygroscopic, meaning it needs to be dried before every print
TPU has good layer adhesion to itself, resulting in few delamination issues in single material parts	TPU does not have good layer adhesion with other types of filaments such as PLA or PETG, making it difficult to use alongside other materials
TPU has a Vicat softening temperature of 110°C, making it suitable for high temperature environments	TPU is more expensive than PLA at £35/kilogram {Bambu Store, April 2026})
TPU is waterproof	TPU is difficult to print, often resulting in stringing or imprecise parts

Table 3: Advantages and Disadvantages of TPU

Aim, Objectives and Hypotheses

The primary **aim** of this project was to develop a multi-material 'hybrid' filament using PLA and TPU that could balance performance, cost-efficiency, and environmental impact (Hereafter, in this document the word “*hybrid*” denote a PLA-TPU mixed material).

We wanted to design a material that:

- Can withstand more impact than PLA
- Is more ductile than PLA
- Has more precise results in prints than when using TPU
- Retains the environmental benefit of using PLA (which is biodegradable)
- Is less expensive than TPU

We were inspired to do this project after experimenting with using multi-colour hobby filaments (filaments typically used for toys, decorations and household fixes) (See Figure 2a and Figure 2b).

**Figure 2a – Black & white split filament
(black side)**

**Figure 2b – Black & white split filament
(white side)**

This type of filament is composed of two or more colours layered on top of one another and can be used to create unique visual effects on a 3D printed part. We wanted to explore if such an approach could be used to create a filament composed of two different materials; something that has, until now, only been accessible to large companies with expensive industrial machinery custom-made to produce and utilise such materials.

Figure 3 – parts printed with a multicolour filament (All3DP, 2024)

This investigation is particularly important to the wider realm of hobbyist and industrial manufacture processes because a true multi-material filament that is both inexpensive and easily available, could significantly improve the cost and durability of 3D-printed parts and enable engineers to tailor the properties of a material to best fit their use-case.

For example, using standard PLA for figurines or gears is best for detail but is brittle. If it falls, small parts can easily shatter. Using a hybrid will make it shatter-proof and less prone to breakage.

We split the overall aim of this project into smaller **objectives**:

- Design and manufacture a hybrid filament
- Conduct performance tests for the hybrid and the single material filaments to give us a holistic view of the materials – tensile strength, heat resistance, compression test, impact test.

We would have achieved our aim if:

- We successfully created a printable hybrid filament
- We successfully managed to conduct performance tests including tensile, heat, compression and impact tests on the hybrid material, recording reliable data
- We arrive at a conclusion whether the performance of the hybrid material was better than PLA or TPU on its own.

Our **hypothesis** was that a hybrid material made from PLA and TPU will inherit properties from PLA and TPU proportionally.

Specifically, the hybrid material will:

- Be less brittle than PLA, but more brittle than TPU
- Be more ductile than PLA, but less ductile than TPU
- Be more impact resistant than PLA, but less impact resistant than TPU
- Be more heat resistant than TPU, but less heat resistant than PLA

Our hypothesis was based on the Rule of Mixtures (Hull and Clyne, 1996) which states that in a composite material, the property of a composite can be estimated by the volume-weighted average of the individual materials.

Approach and Options

Options considered for manufacturing the hybrid filament

Originally, we brainstormed and debated many methods of manufacturing the hybrid material. The options considered are shown below in Table 4.

Method:	Pros:	Cons:
Injection Moulding	Efficient and precise	Equipment needed is not easily available for use for this project, and exceeded our budget
Traditional filament extrusion	Well documented and used by professionals	Equipment needed is not easily available for use for this project and exceeded our budget
Hybrid Printed filament (“core” Method)	Can easily be done with only a 3D printer as well as better material combination	Difficult to print due to bad adhesion between PLA and TPU
Hybrid Printed filament (“split” Method)	Can easily be done with only a 3D printer – easy to print	The PLA and TPU do not combine as evenly as the core method

Table 4: Comparison of methods for manufacturing the hybrid filament

Due to the prohibitive equipment costs for injection moulding and traditional filament extrusion, we decided to go with the hybrid printed filament methods. We identified two possible ways to create this hybrid material – through a “core” or “split” method.

The core method involved printing some PLA filament with a fibrous TPU core, as in the cross-sectional diagram shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 – Core method cross-sectional diagram

We hypothesised that this method would be strong and shatter-resistant due to the PLA being stacked upon itself during the deposition process and the TPU acting as a continuous fibre running through the part. However, we also suspected that the thin TPU fibre could prove challenging to manufacture.

The second method we devised was a more traditional split filament as shown in Figure 5. By having the two materials on top of one another, they would be easier to print, but the part produced might be brittle.

Figure 5 – Split filament cross-sectional diagram

We decided to explore these two approaches over the rest due to their cost-effectiveness and relative ease.

We ended up using the split filament method, due to ease of printing, after we had several failed attempts with the core method. This is explained in subsequent sections.

Options considered for testing the materials

Initially, we considered manufacturing and testing different ratios of PLA to TPU – 25:75, 50:50 and 75:25. However, due to budget constraints and time constraints, we manufactured and tested only the 50:50 hybrid filament and compared against pure PLA and pure TPU.

Project Timeline

To successfully produce and test these materials, we devised the following 4-phase plan.

Phase 1 – Initiation and planning:

- Initial brainstorm and planning - develop project aim, objectives and hypothesis
- Secure resources and mentoring support
- Consult with teachers on initial plan and hypothesis
- Create initial design and test plans
- Consult with mentors about test processes and how to use school equipment

Phase 2 – Design and manufacturing hybrid material:

- Create 3D models of the “core” and “split” style multimaterial filaments
- Initial prototyping with TPU and PLA, iterate design
- Manufacture (3D print) multimaterial filaments
- Manufacture (3D print) test pieces
- Build test rigs
- Initial tests with single material filament test pieces (PLA/TPU)

Phase 3 – Testing materials:

- Formal Risk Assessment for all tests
- Conduct Tensile Test
- Conduct Heat Test
- Conduct Compression Test
- Conduct Impact Test

Phase 4 – Draw conclusions and project write-up:

- Draw conclusions from the results of the tests
- Evaluate the effectiveness of our methods for producing and testing the materials
- Evaluate the success of our multimaterial filament
- Prepare report (including iterations)

We mapped out key dependencies for the project. For example, for each test, we had to make sure that the custom test pieces were designed and printed before conducting the test. We also made sure that we built in some time as buffer in our plan, in case of unforeseen delays.

A Gantt chart of our project showing the timeline over 8 months and task responsibilities is shown below.

Figure 6 – Project Gantt Chart

Designing and manufacturing the hybrid filament

To design the hybrid filament, we first created a virtual model using SolidWorks (standard 3D design software). In order to design the filament, we first used the helix tool in SolidWorks to create a flat spiral. Next, we sketched the cross-sectional profile of the filament perpendicularly to one end of the spiral and swept it along the spiral. Throughout the design process we had to keep in mind that our designs would be 3D printed, so we could not have steep overhangs or small surface areas contacting the build plate.

We then convert our model into G-CODE using Bambu Studio. G-CODE is the list of instructions that tells a 3D printer how to create a part.

We decided that going with the “core” method (as discussed in the previous section and shown in Figure 4) would be best, as the TPU would provide a continuous strengthened fibre that would run through the whole filament.

To manufacture (print) the hybrid filament, we used a Bambu P1S 3D printer. However, we encountered great difficulty when attempting to manufacture it. The high viscosity of the TPU when passing through the Hotend (i.e., component of the printer that heats and melts the filament) meant that it adhered too quickly to the PLA outer. The PLA would then be dragged off the print bed by the TPU, as there was very little contact area between the PLA and print bed. This would cause a serious failure, causing the TPU to not have a surface to be printed on, causing a ‘spaghetti failure’ (see Figure 7).

Figure 7 – ‘Spaghetti’ failure of core filament design

After multiple iterations with the same results, we eventually rejected the ‘core’ method and switched to our “split” filament design (as discussed in the previous section and

shown in Figure 5). Due to the thicker deposits of PLA and TPU we expected that they would better bond together and the print would succeed.

As expected, – this time the filament mostly printed successfully, but there was still stringing near the ends, due to low bed adhesion (see Figure 8). To try and prevent this we added two tabs to the ends of the filament spiral, increasing the contact area, and hence the bed adhesion (see Figure 9).

Figure 8 – Stringing while printing split filament

Figure 9 – Filament design with tabs

This was very successful and gave us perfect results c.90% of the time.

Printing with the hybrid filament

When we first tried printing with the hybrid filament, we opted to do so on an older “Ender-3” model of printer. We chose this particular model of the printer it is a moving-bed Cartesian printer, allowing us to disassemble it and more easily clear material jams that we predicted could arise when printing with the hybrid filament.

However, the simpler design of the Ender 3 model was also very inefficient – the hotend of this old model has a shorter melt zone than modern designs, which reduced the hybrid material’s ability to mix and combine during printing. Figure 10 shows a comparison of the hotend design of the two printers.

Figure 10 – Melt zone comparison between newer (left, Bambu Lab P1S) and older (right, Ender 3) hotend designs

This phenomenon was to blame for the stringy layers experienced with some of our earlier test pieces.

To counteract this, we opted to switch to a newer Bambu Lab P1S printer after confirming that the hybrid material was safe to print, by testing it on less expensive Ender 3 printer. The Bambu Lab printer has a higher residence time (time spent in the melt zone), which improved material mixing and resulted in far stronger parts.

However, even with the Bambu Lab P1S, we continued encountering further issues when attempting to print with the TPU. The corners were very under-extruded, which could severely decrease its material properties. To troubleshoot this we tried several methods, such as recalibrating input shaping and using a different nozzle. Eventually we discovered that the k-factor of the material was almost double its correct value within the printer’s presets, and decreasing it solved our issues.

Testing the Materials

First, we brainstormed the following six holistic assessments which could appropriately quantify the performance of the hybrid material:

- Tensile Test
- Heat Test
- Compression Test
- Impact Test
- Weathering Test
- Hardness Test

Then, we fine-tuned the tests with the help of our mentors - Mr. Chandler and Mr. Rothman. After discussion, we agreed to conduct the tensile, heat, compression and impact tests on the hybrid material. Our mentors provided advice on which tests would be feasible to conduct in a school environment, as well as risk and safety advice (Risk Assessment included in Appendix A). We designed appropriate custom test pieces for each of these tests and printed them in single materials (PLA and TPU) and the hybrid PLA/TPU 50:50 material to assess their relative performance.

We decided to reject the Weathering test as it would span a long period of time, which could not be added to the project plan at that stage. Our ideas for the weathering test included UV exposure and attrition exposure.

We decided to reject the Hardness test as a Durometer was not readily available at school. We had considered conducting a Shore D Hardness Test.

Tensile Test:

Understanding the tensile strength of a material is important as it provides quantitative, reliable data on how much force a material can withstand before deforming permanently or failing entirely. Since TPU is a more elastic material, we decided to base this test off the Young's Modulus of the material, which indicates how stiff or elastic a material is. With the help of Mr Rothman, we adapted the standard Young's Modulus test which is typically performed as part of A-level Physics. We adapted certain parts of the test to work with 2-metre-long lengths of filament. We used a 2m long piece of filament so that there would be a more significant, measurable extension (ΔL).

Heat Test:

Since 3D printed parts are often used in high temperature environments, we wanted to compare the thermal stability of the materials under intense heat. We compared the heat endurance of the hybrid against PLA and TPU by focussing on the Glass Transition

Temperature – this is the temperature at which the polymers change its physical state from rigid and brittle to soft, flexible and rubbery.

Compression Test:

3D printed parts are used for functional pieces that are often placed under large, static, compressive load, which makes it important to understand how a material copes under compressive force. In this test, we applied horizontal forces to the specimen parallel and perpendicularly to the layer lines. We measured the change in width of the specimen (which was due to the application of the compressive force).

Impact test:

Finally, we wanted to explore which material which could withstand the highest impact. In this test, we compared the impact strength of the three different materials. By adapting a standard Izod Impact test, we designed a testing rig which used a hammer as a swinging pendulum, so that the same energy could be delivered to the specimen every time. We measured the rise angle of the hammer, which was directly correlated to the energy delivered to the specimen.

Tensile Test

Materials

- 2x G-clamps
- 3x Pieces of wood
- Pulley
- 20x 100g weights + weight holder
- 150mm Steel rule
- Specimens (3x 2m long strips of filament (\varnothing 1.75mm): PLA, TPU and Hybrid)
- Needle
- Masking tape
- Bespoke hook (glued to filament)

Method

1. Clamp the filament between two pieces of wood, and clamp that to the table
2. Fix the pulley on a piece of wood and clamp it to the table
3. Place the other end of the filament on the pulley
4. Fix the steel rule to the table with masking tape.
5. Fix the needle on the filament with masking tape, so it is in line with the 150mm mark
6. Add weight to the end of the filament, one hundred grams at a time, and measure where the needle points to after each increase
7. Measure the extension of the filament by taking a measurement from where the needle aligns with the steel rule.
8. Calculate the Young's modulus of each filament

Observations

During the test, we noticed that the filament did not begin to extend until it was taut – something which was impossible to achieve only with a clamp, as the other end of the filament was on the pulley.

See Figure 11 (images A-D) for details of the experimental setup.

Gallery

Figure 11 – Images A-D from the tensile test showing experimental setup and fiduciary marker needle

Data and Results

In this test a higher extension (under the application of 19.6 N) indicates a lower stiffness. As you can see from Figure 12, TPU extended to a maximum of 12mm (under a constant force of 19.6N) compared to 3.5 mm for PLA, and 4mm for the hybrid material, meaning TPU is the least stiff of the three materials, while PLA has the highest stiffness (highest resistance to elastic deformation). The hybrid material performed in between PLA and TPU, but it only had a marginally higher extension than PLA. For each specific load, TPU consistently had a higher extension than the other materials.

However, the extension of the hybrid material was always within 0.5mm of the PLA, meaning it inherited more of the tensile properties of PLA than TPU.

Figure 12 - Tensile test results showing extension of PLA, TPU and Split materials under varying force

We calculated the Young's Modulus of the different materials for each reading we took. We then calculated the mean and median of these values to compare the different materials.

$$\text{Young's Modulus} = \frac{\text{Tensile Stress}}{\text{Tensile Strain}} = \frac{F \cdot L}{A \Delta L}, \text{ where :}$$

- F = force (N)
- L = original length (m)
- A = cross-sectional area (m²)
- ΔL = extension (m)

Figure 13 – Comparison of Young's Modulus

As you can see from the results shown in Figure 13, the Young's Modulus of the hybrid material (mean value 4667.7 MPa) is between PLA (mean value 5034.3 MPa) and TPU (mean value 1089.9 MPa). Overall, the results partially supported our initial hypothesis.

While the Young's modulus of the hybrid material is in between PLA and TPU as expected, it is much closer to PLA than to TPU, contradicting our hypothesis that the 50:50 hybrid material would be in the middle of PLA and TPU as expected from the rule of mixtures.

This means that the hybrid material would not perform significantly better than the PLA in situations where high elasticity is needed.

We also note that we later compared them with the official values from Bambu Lab's *Technical Data Sheet*. The official values were:

- 2580 ± 220 MPa – PLA Basic (Bambu Lab, 2024)
- 1190 ± 0.4 MPa – TPU for AMS (Bambu Lab, 2023)

We concluded that these discrepancies were most likely due to parallax error while taking readings and routine variation in a school test setup.

Heat Test

Materials

- Heat Gun (rated output of 460°C)
- 2x retort stand
- Boss
- Test Specimens (3x 2,4,6,8mm thickness test pieces for PLA, TPU and Hybrid) – See note and Figure 13 for dimensions and design
- Stopwatch
- Ruler

For this test, we designed the heat test specimen (Figure 14) in such a way, that the two notches on either side are the point of deflection. During the planning phase, we tried the heat test with only a rectangle and found that there was no clear deflection, proving the need for a designed point of failure.

Figure 14 – CAD model and dimensions for the heat test specimen

Method

To carry out the heat test, we initially wanted to use a Bunsen Burner, however, the risk assessment concluded that this would be unsafe, due to the potential presence of harmful gases, when the specimens would come in contact with the naked flame. This

forced us to explore our options, and to effectively mitigate the risk, we had to borrow a temperature-adjustable Heat Gun from the DE department for the final experiment.

1. Set the heat gun vertically.
2. Align the centre of the heat gun's nozzle with the designed point of failure
3. Use a boss and stand to clamp the specimen horizontally 8 cm above the heat gun's nozzle (so the specimen does not melt onto and damage the heat gun)
4. for 20-40 seconds.
5. Remove the specimen and allow to cool
6. Trace the curvature of the change of the specimen onto a piece of graph paper and measure the deflection. We measured the deflection by drawing a perpendicular line from the end of the original test piece and measure the distance from the original test piece to the heated test piece. (see Figure 15)

Figure 15 – How we measured the deflection

Observations

All test pieces deflected from the designed point of failure.

The hybrid TPU+PLA test piece also displayed annealing-like properties near the site where it had been heated (Figure 16). This was good news, because it indicated that it may be possible to anneal parts printed with the hybrid filament – a process in which 3D printed parts are heated in a controlled environment to strengthen them by better fusing the layers together.

Figure 16– 8mm specimen showing annealing properties

On the day of testing, we were unable to use the results from the 2mm test specimens because some of them had deformed too far. However, this enabled us to finetune the heating duration for the 4mm, 6mm and 8mm specimens. See Figure 17 (images E-H) for details of the setup.

Gallery

Figure 17 – Images E-H from the Heat test showing experimental setup and the diagrams drawn to measure a reading

Data and Results

In these tests, a smaller deflection indicates a greater heat endurance.

Due to a higher Glass Transition Temperature, PLA had a relatively high heat endurance as compared to TPU. Since all the specimens were being subject to intense heat from a 460° C output rated heat-gun, this was pushing them to their limits. 3D printed parts are not typically subject to these levels of thermal stress, but functional parts used in engines or model rockets, often require materials that can endure this.

As you can see from Figures 18,19 and 20, the hybrid material, as hypothesised, consistently performed between the PLA and TPU.

In the 4mm test (Figure 18), the magnitude of deflection of the hybrid specimen was closer to TPU than PLA. However, in the 6mm test (Figure 19), the hybrid specimen performed closer to the PLA than the TPU. Finally, in the 8mm test (Figure 20), the hybrid material performed exactly in between PLA and TPU.

This shows that while the heat endurance of the specimens is correlated to the thickness of the specimen, the heat endurance of the hybrid was in between PLA and TPU, confirming our hypothesis. This suggests that the hybrid material is more suitable than TPU in higher temperature use cases.

Figure 18 – Heat test data for 4 mm test piece

Figure 19 – Heat test data for 6 mm test piece

Figure 20 – Heat test data for 8 mm test piece

Compression Test

Materials

- Table vice
- Specimens (2x 20mm³ cube in PLA, TPU and 50:50 Hybrid Filament)

Method

1. Place 20mm³ cube in vice
2. Horizontally compress the specimen in a vice the 2 vice plates are 18 mm apart from each other
3. Remove specimen from vice, and measure the deformation as the change in width of the specimen
4. Repeat this test twice for each specimen material. Compress the specimen parallel to the layer lines for one, and the other, parallel to the layer lines

Observations

The PLA specimens experienced brittle failures, whereas the TPU and Hybrid specimens experienced plastic failure, under the application of the same compressive force.

Plastic failure is more desirable because a functional part suddenly shattering under load could be catastrophic, and result in significant losses. However, a part that fails over a longer period of time allows us to define a “*predictable path of failure*”

We observed in the PLA specimens that the top layers delaminated from the rest of the test piece indicating poor adhesion between the infill material and the walls (shown in Figure 21):

Figure 21 – PLA Specimen with top layer come off

See Figure 22 (images I-M) for details of the test set up.

Gallery

Figure 22 – Images I-M from the compression test showing the compressed test pieces

Data and Results

In this test, a lower change in width indicates higher pressure resistance.

As you can see from Figure 23, the hybrid material (3mm change) performed in between the PLA (2.5mm change) and TPU (4mm change), when compressed perpendicularly to the layer lines.

However, as seen in Figure 24, when the specimen was compressed parallel to the layer lines, the hybrid specimen performed better than both PLA and TPU. We noticed

that this result was due to the way that PLA bonds with TPU - we obtained this result because there were alternate layers of PLA and TPU, providing a ‘cushioning’ effect as shown in Figure 25. This shows that the hybrid material is more suited to high pressure environments than PLA and TPU when compressed parallel to the layer lines.

The test conducted perpendicular to the layer lines confirms our hypothesis, as the hybrid material performed in between the PLA and TPU. However, the test conducted parallel to the layer lines, does not confirm our hypothesis, as the hybrid performs better than both the PLA and TPU.

Figure 23 – Compression test data (perpendicular to layer lines)

Figure 24 – Compression test data (parallel to layer lines)

Figure 25 – Pressure diagram of specimen

Impact Test

Iterations

Our initial proposed test was quite rudimentary, which forced us to redesign the setup to ensure it was a fair, repeatable test. We had 3 iterations of the test setup:

- **Iteration 1:** We would clamp the test piece to the table and just use a hammer to break it. This would not prove to be a reliable test as we couldn't control the force of the hammer
- **Iteration 2:** We would hang the hammer from a dowel/string and swing it from a set angle at the test piece. However, this would also not be reliable as the position of the hammer would change each time and the hammer had a chance of flying off the string
- **Iteration 3:** We designed a bespoke hammer hub with two low friction bearings, which allowed us to connect it so a simple wooden rig and seamlessly start using the hammer as a swinging pendulum, so the same energy would be delivered to the specimen every time.

Eventually, we decided to use Iteration 3, as it could deliver the same amount of energy every time, and allowed us to repeat the tests multiple times.

Materials

- Hammer rotation hub
- Bench vice (to hold test subject)
- 2x quick clamps (to fasten test rig to table)
- 2x planks of wood
- Specimens (2,4,6 and 8mm thick test pieces – PLA, TPU and 50:50 Hybrid) – see Figure 26 for test specimen design

Figure 26 – CAD model and dimensions for the impact test specimen

Method

1. Attach a plank of wood perpendicularly to the middle of another plank
2. Screw the hammer hub to the end of the plank of wood
3. Use two screws to attach the hammer to the hub, and use zip ties to stabilise it
4. Use two G-clamps to fasten the bottom of the hammer stand to the bench, in front of a clamp
5. Fasten the test specimen in the clamp, so it is aligned with the hammer's path, and the notch was facing the hammer
6. Pull the hammer back 20° (defined as the Rise Angle) and release it so it hits the test specimen above the notch
7. If the test specimen remains unharmed (e.g. no layer splitting/cracks), then increase the rise angle by 10°
8. Repeat step 7 until the specimen breaks
9. Record the rise angle at which the specimen breaks (see Figure 27)

Figure 27 – Schematic diagram showing rise angle

Observations

During the impact test we noticed that some of the test pieces were splitting along the layer lines before breaking across the designed fracture point. This is due to poor layer adhesion qualities between PLA and TPU. See Figure 28 (images N-Q) for details of the set up.

We initially wanted to measure the force at which the hammer hit the specimen. However, in discussion with Mr. Rothman, we realised that we had to time the impact, which we could not do with the equipment available in the labs, as it requires a very high degree of precision. This is why we decided to measure the strength of the specimens based on the breakage angle instead

Gallery

Figure 28 – Images from the Impact test showing experimental setup and impacted test pieces

Data and Results

In this test, a higher rise angle allows the pendulum to impart a higher energy to the specimen, indicating a material with higher impact strength. For example, the rise angle at which the specimen broke (henceforth called the Breakage Angle), for the 6mm specimens were 100° for TPU (Figure 31), 30° for the PLA specimen, and 50° for the hybrid material, performing in between PLA and TPU. This pattern was evident across all tests (as seen in figures 29 - 32). This shows that the hybrid material is more ductile than PLA, but more brittle than TPU, making it more suitable than PLA for high impact use cases, or for thinner, more detailed parts. This confirms our hypothesis as the hybrid performs in between PLA and TPU.

We note that:

1. In the 6mm test piece, the TPU test piece did not break even at 100°. While we could've continued with greater angles, the risk assessment deemed that this was unsafe, as the test piece could shatter violently. This is why we decided to record it as breaking at 100°

Figure 29 – Impact test results for 2 mm test piece

Figure 30 – Impact test results for 4mm test piece

Figure 31 – Impact test results for 6mm test piece

Figure 32 – Impact test data for 8mm test piece

Discussion and Conclusion

In this project we had set out to develop and investigate the performance of hybrid materials in 3D printing, specifically a hybrid material made from PLA and TPU.

We were able to successfully design and develop a hybrid filament which can be printed easily even in domestic or school settings. The decisions made during developing this material, and how they affected the outcome of the project, are summarised in Table 5 below.

Factor	Action	Outcome
Which materials to use to create the hybrid material	We used PLA and TPU	We successfully created a printable hybrid material. Since we used PLA and TPU, there were no issues with the print temperature or calibration
How to create the hybrid material	We utilised a split method with tabs to print the filament	The hybrid material filament was easy to print. Since we used the split filament, we reduced the number of filament changes needed to print it. The tabs increased the contact area with the print bed, reducing chances of it becoming detached
Which tests to use to evaluate the strength of the hybrid material	We used tensile, heat, compression and impact tests	We managed to holistically evaluate the hybrid material, and compare it to PLA and TPU separately

Table 5: How our actions affected the outcomes of this project

With regards to the performance of the hybrid material, it confirmed our hypothesis that it would inherit the advantageous properties of both PLA and TPU. However, there were differences in how the hybrid material performed in each test (see Table 6 below).

Test	Performance of Hybrid
Tensile	This was the least convincing test. It indicated that in terms of tensile strength, the hybrid material is only marginally stronger than PLA, making it unsuitable for use cases where there is a heavy load on one part
Heat	This test showed that the hybrid material's heat resistance is exactly in between that of PLA and TPU. However, its heat resistance is greatly dependant on the thickness of the use case
Compression	This test showed that when compressed parallel to the layer lines, the hybrid material is stronger than both the PLA and TPU, making it more suitable than both of them for parts like 3D printed spring, which undergo a lot of compression
Impact	This was the most convincing test. It shows that the addition of TPU, can make PLA shatter and impact resistant, making it useful for situations with small parts or high impact, when normal TPU is not suitable

Table 6: Summary and conclusion of each test

Based on our observations, we conclude that the hybrid material could be very useful in certain cases where these kinds of semi-flexible properties are needed, such as the flex spline of a harmonic drive, as part of a series elastic actuator, or 3D printed springs.

It is worth noting (per our research) that the properties of the hybrid filament are similar to those of Polyethylene Terephthalate Glycol (PETG), a thermoplastic that is commonly used in 3D printing. However, our hybrid filament already offers several advantages over PETG. The hybrid filament is more sustainable and cheaper to produce and print with, at a lower scale, such as when prototyping parts. It is also significantly easier to design parts for the hybrid material, as it performs better when printing overhangs and bridges, and does not experience warping when printing on low-grip surfaces.

In the future we think it would be worth comparing the properties of hybrid filament to the properties of other thermoplastics, and the advantages of multimaterial filament during printing. This is discussed further in the Reflection section.

Reflection

Overall, in this investigation we achieved our aim of creating an easy-to-manufacture, easy-to-print, and cost-effective multimaterial filament that gained the advantageous properties of PLA and TPU. The tests we devised to measure the properties of the materials were successful in doing so, to a high repeatability and accuracy.

However, if we were to repeat this investigation, there are several things upon which we could improve. For example, the parts manufactured from the multimaterial filament were often too flexible for use in most applications and printed poorly on older 3D printers. An interesting extension of this project could be developing the hybrid material so that it is compatible with all types of 3D printer.

Due to time and material constraints, we could not repeat our tests during this project, which could have led to more reliable data, and removed anomalies. Were we to repeat the investigation where time and money were not constraints, we would be much more rigorous in our testing by incorporating more accurate methods for measuring results and repeat the tests multiple times.

We also think it could have been beneficial to test several different ratios of PLA:TPU (20:80,40:60,60:40,80:20) within the filament, with the aim of reaching a ratio with which the parts manufactured from the hybrid filament were as stiff as PLA under standard use but could flex like TPU under load.

If we were to repeat this investigation, we would change the following factors:

- In general:
 - We would repeat each test several times, to make sure our results were more reliable and accurate
 - We would test the hybrid materials with different ratios of PLA:TPU (20:80,30:70,40:60,60:40,70:30,80:20)
 - We would manufacture the hybrid material with different original materials, such as those detailed at the beginning
 - We would test the hybrid materials with different styles and percentages of infill
- In the Tensile test:
 - We would design a bespoke needle holder, to get more precise results than using masking tape
 - We would use an electronic micrometre to measure the extension, to eliminate parallax error

- In the Heat test:
 - o We would use an infrared thermometer to measure the exact temperature the specimen is heated to
- In the Compression test:
 - o We would calculate the compressive force on each test piece
- In the Impact test:
 - o We would use a camera and millisecond stopwatch to time the impact, so we could calculate the force applied

Through doing this project we developed many of our knowledge and skills related to research, engineering, and science.

While planning the project we developed our research skills to find out about the possible methods for creating and printing with multimaterial filaments, and the previous attempts to do so.

Through this research we learnt about the industrial processes behind creating 3D printing filament, the inner workings of a 3D printer's hotend, the numerous materials utilised in 3D printing, and their individual properties.

We also learnt about the techniques used to quantitatively measure the properties of materials and how important accurate measurements are for calculating the force at which a part may fail.

When creating the tests we learnt how to use Computer-Aided Design to create accurate and repeatable test rigs and test specimens, and we learnt about the importance of allowing for tolerances and other manufacture inconsistencies when designing parts.

We also developed our collaboration skills when working with our teachers to plan and produce these investigations, and when working together to equally assign tasks related to the project.

We learnt how to create a project plan, and a Gantt chart. This was particularly important, as we had baked in contingencies which became useful when we could not perform a test on a specific day.

While writing up our project, we also learnt several key skills about how to create an academic paper, such as how to create a table of contents, and how to appropriately cite sources and create a bibliography.

In summary, this was a highly rewarding and enriching project which increased our depth of knowledge about this subject.

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Appendix

Risk Assessment

Before we conducted each test, we conducted a risk assessment to minimise chances of injury to the participants, and/or damage to equipment. For each risk, we assigned it a ‘likelihood of risk’ and ‘risk severity level’, on a scale of 1-5, with one being the least likely/dangerous, and five being the most. For each risk we have included a way to mitigate the risk, so that the tests were as safe as possible.

Tensile test

Likelihood of risk	Severity of risk	Risks	Who could be harmed	Actions we have taken to mitigate risks
3	1	Being pricked by indicator needle	Leonid (reading results), Mr Rothman (setting up experiment)	Keep hands away from needle when reading measurements, let a responsible adult set up the experiment
3	2	Dropping weights on body parts	Rehan (handling weights)	Be careful when manoeuvring with weights
3	2	Filament snapping	All	Make sure weights are properly connected to filament hook

Heat test

Likelihood of risk	Severity of risk	Risks	Who could be harmed	Actions we have taken to mitigate risks
4	4	Burns from heat gun	Leonid (handling test samples), Mr Rothman (operating heat gun)	Keep hands far away from heat gun nozzle
3	4	Burns from melted plastic test samples	Leonid (handling test samples)	Handle samples by the end furthest from the heat gun. Allowing time for them to cool down before touching heated sections
3	2	Inhaling fumes from melting plastic	All	Performing experiment in well-ventilated area

Compression test

Likelihood of risk	Severity of risk	Risks	Who could be harmed	Actions we have taken to mitigate risks
4	2	Touching loose splinters of plastic	Rehan (handling test samples)	Wear gloves + goggles
3	3	Clamping body parts in vice	Rehan (handling + clamping test samples)	Control position of hands during clamping

Impact test

Likelihood of risk	Severity of risk	Risks	Who could be harmed	Actions we have taken to mitigate risks
3	4	Being hit by swinging hammer	Leonid (swinging hammer)	Keep hands far away from hammer until it stops swinging, release hammer a safe distance from the test piece
3	3	Touching loose splinters of plastic	Rehan (handling test samples)	Wear gloves and goggles
2	2	Clamping body parts in vice	Rehan (handling + clamping test samples)	Control position of hands during clamping
2	4	Hammer coming loose from rig	All	Ensure hammer is well-affixed to the test rig with screws

Supplementary Figures

All specimens from Imact test

All specimens from Heat test:

Raw Data from Tests

Tensile Test – Raw Data

PLA					Hybrid					TPU							
Length		1.91 m			Length		1.92 m			Length		1.79 m					
Area		2.40 mm ²			Area		2.40 mm ²			Area		2.40 mm ²					
force (N)	mass (kg)	Raw Reading	Extension (mm)	Young's Modulus (calc.)	force (N)	mass (kg)	Raw Reading	Extensio n (mm)	Young's Modulus (calc.)	force (N)	mass (kg)	Raw Reading	Extensio n (mm)	Young's Modulus (calc.)			
0.98	0.1	-	0.0		0.98	0.1	-	0.0		0.98	0.1	149.5	0.0				
1.96	0.2	151.0	0.0		1.96	0.2	149.0	0.0		1.96	0.2	147	2.5	582.1			
2.94	0.3	150.5	0.5	4671.6	2.94	0.3	149.0	0.0		2.94	0.3	147	2.5	873.2			
3.92	0.4	150.5	0.5	6228.8	3.92	0.4	148.5	0.5	6261.4	3.92	0.4	146	3.5	831.6			
4.90	0.5	150.5	0.5	7786.0	4.90	0.5	148.5	0.5	7826.8	4.90	0.5	145	4.5	808.5			
5.88	0.6	150.0	1.0	4671.6	5.88	0.6	148.0	1.0	4696.1	5.88	0.6	144.5	5.0	873.2			
6.86	0.7	150.0	1.0	5450.2	6.86	0.7	148.0	1.0	5478.7	6.86	0.7	144	5.5	926.1			
7.84	0.8	150.0	1.0	6228.8	7.84	0.8	147.5	1.5	4174.3	7.84	0.8	144	5.5	1058.4			
8.82	0.9	149.5	1.5	4671.6	8.82	0.9	147.5	1.5	4696.1	8.82	0.9	143.5	6.0	1091.5			
9.80	1.0	149.5	1.5	5190.7	9.80	1.0	147.5	1.5	5217.8	9.80	1.0	142.5	7.0	1039.5			
10.78	1.1	149.5	1.5	5709.7	10.78	1.1	147.0	2.0	4304.7	10.78	1.1	142.5	7.0	1143.4			
11.76	1.2	149.0	2.0	4671.6	11.76	1.2	147.0	2.0	4696.1	11.76	1.2	142	7.5	1164.2			
12.74	1.3	149.0	2.0	5060.9	12.74	1.3	146.5	2.5	4069.9	12.74	1.3	141.5	8.0	1182.4			
13.72	1.4	148.5	2.5	4360.2	13.72	1.4	146.5	2.5	4383.0	13.72	1.4	141.5	8.0	1273.4			
14.70	1.5	148.5	2.5	4671.6	14.70	1.5	146.0	3.0	3913.4	14.70	1.5	141	8.5	1284.1			
15.68	1.6	148.0	3.0	4152.5	15.68	1.6	146.0	3.0	4174.3	15.68	1.6	140	9.5	1225.5			
16.66	1.7	148.0	3.0	4412.1	16.66	1.7	145.5	3.5	3801.6	16.66	1.7	139.5	10.0	1237.0			
17.64	1.8	147.5	3.5	4004.2	17.64	1.8	145.5	3.5	4025.2	17.64	1.8	138.5	11.0	1190.7			
18.62	1.9	147.5	3.5	4226.7	18.62	1.9	145.0	4.0	3717.7	18.62	1.9	138	11.5	1202.2			
19.60	2.0	147.5	3.5	4449.1	19.60	2.0	145.0	4.0	3913.4	19.60	2.0	137.5	12.0	1212.7			
PLA				Mean	5034.3	Hybrid				Mean	4667.7	TPU				Mean	1089.9
				Median	4671.6					Median	4304.7					Median	1153.8

Heat Test – Raw Data

Specimen	PLA	Hybrid	TPU	
4mm	Length change (mm)	12.5	27.5	34
	Rate (mm/s)	0.42	0.92	1.13
6mm	Length change (mm)	18	18.5	21.5
	Rate (mm/s)	0.45	0.46	0.54
8mm	Length change (mm)	6	16	26
	Rate (mm/s)	0.15	0.4	0.65

Compression Test – Raw Data

Z-UP (Perpendicular to layer lines)

	PLA	Hybrid	TPU
Start	18 mm	18 mm	18 mm
End	16.5 mm	15 mm	14 mm
Change	2.5 mm	3 mm	4 mm

Y-UP (Parallel to layer lines)

	PLA	Hybrid	TPU
Start	19 mm	19 mm	19 mm
End	15.3 mm	14.5 mm	14.1 mm
Change	4 mm	3.5 mm	5 mm

Impact Test – Raw Data

2 mm thick specimen	PLA	Hybrid	TPU
Rise Angle at which specimen breaks (°)	30	40	50
4 mm thick specimen	PLA	Hybrid	TPU
Rise Angle at which specimen breaks (°)	30	40	60
6 mm thick specimen	PLA	Hybrid	TPU
Rise Angle at which specimen breaks (°)	30	50	100
8 mm thick specimen	PLA	Hybrid	TPU
Rise Angle at which specimen breaks (°)	40	40	60

Notes:

- We were not allowed to use our phones during the compression test, meaning that we could not take photos of the experimental setup
- For all specimens we used standard grid infill, with an infill density of 15%
- All specimens were printed on a Bambu Lab P1S model of 3D printer
- We tried to make tests as fair as possible – using the same setup and specimens, but discrepancies may be present.